

VALKYRIES

D1.5 Data Management Platform

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the Data Management Platform developed for the VALKYRIES project under T1.5.

It includes three sections: the first one refers to a guided system to fill the data management plan, according to the instructions described in D1.3, D1.16 and D1.17 aiming to collect and curate data as open as possible and as close as necessary; the second one refers to guidelines for first responders and, more generally innovators, dealing with emergency scenarios in order to enable data sharing under the current EU Data Strategy as described in D3.3, D1.4, D1.19 and a section dedicated to the ethics and diversity management, already delivered in D1.6 and here updated as described in D1.19.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Data Management Platform

Deliverable Id: D1.5

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D1.5

Name of lead participant: SSSA

Name of Contributors: All partners

Type: Report (R)

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

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Linked project tasks: T1.5 - Ethical and Legal compliance framework

Action: Design

Status: First Release

Document Layout: VALKYRIES official template

Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. The document illustrates protocols for innovators to facilitate the compliance activities with the current ethical legal framework.

3. Document and Project Scope

This is the report illustrating the demonstrator aiming to drive the ethical-legal compliance in Research & Development & Innovation sectors.

Starting from the procedures developed in VALKYRIES, the report illustrates the guidelines embedded in a SaaS platform open to stakeholders. These may find application in each step of the life-cycle of the R&D&I activities despite of the type of the designed technology or solution.

3.1. Project Overview

The Deliverable combines the research and compliance overview of the VALKYRIES ecosystem. It shows how regulation, standardisation, and compliance are fully integrated by the principle of accountability.

3.2. Document Structure

The Document illustrates the three sections of the VALKYRIES Data Management Platform.

4.3. Requirements traceability matrix

Description of the requirements can be consulted in D2.7 – Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases document.

Each task leader should add the results and check the deliverables column. Note that required requirements must be achieved at the end of the project.

ID	Priority	Traceability	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T 1.5_2 ND	P1	OBJ 2	D1.5	Inspection	Section DMP

Table 1 – Requirements compliance matrix

4. The VALKYRIES SaaS Data Management Platform

The ethical-legal unit developed platform to provide a user-friendly interface aiming to disseminate the reports and the research results in terms of practical guidelines for innovators.

The Data Management Platform includes the links to the reports developed during the VALKYRIES project including the Data Management Plan, the Ethics and Diversity Report and the Protocols for innovators both in the preliminary and in the final versions.

In addition, the platform includes a series of practical checklists and instructions for first responders and innovators aiming to start a life-cycle of Research & Development & Innovation both in the sector of first response and disaster recovery actions and more in general in possible data-driven initiatives.

The main objective is to provide a series of open access smart tools able to contribute to responsible R&D&I through a series of guidelines and instructions that are combining an accountable approach towards the ethical legal issues emerging in data-driven activities.

Disclaimer: users shall be aware that guidelines are general ones and shall be adapted to the evolution of the applicable ethical-legal framework. They are a useful instrument to deal with ethical legal compliance, but they are not replacing any ethical legal tailored advice.

To this end, SSSA has been supported by Noze s.r.l.¹ that developed a SaaS tool based on the open source web framework Form.io and the NoSQL database engine MongoDB.

During the development the Platform has been firstly internally tested and discussed among the SSSA unit, then among the Consortium and finally at the fourth ethical legal workshop on September 19th 2023. Useful feedback has been embedded to improve the usability of the platform.

In the next paragraphs, a more detailed description of the different sections is provided.

¹ Order n. 1602 del 23/06/2023. CUP: J55F21002980006. CIG: Z7D3BAACE6

5. Section 1: Data Management Plan

The Data Management Plan SaaS is available at this link: <https://demo.valkyries-h2020.eu/data.html>

This section is divided into two parts.

The first part includes a series of instructions and principles emerging from the VALKYRIES experience, serving as operative guidelines that could find application either in first response scenarios or in any other kind of R&D&I context.

In alignment with the DMP developed in VALKYRIES and the research developed to address the ethical legal issues emerging from the fragmented applicable framework analysed in D3.1 and boost the interoperability as investigated under D3.3, the policies and recommendations are developed considering the different players in data collection, data access, and data sharing, focusing as well as on the different purposes for data management.

In fact, within VALKYRIES ecosystem data processing is generally justified under the emergency cases, while it is relevant to address the conditions to provide suggestions on data sharing (as open as possible and as close as necessary) also once that the emergency context has been solved.

The human-centric perspective aiming to ensure and promote data subjects' rights is the key-goal of these guidelines.

Introduction	A. Policies and recommendations	A.1. Collection of data	A.2. Access to data	A.3. Secondary use of data	A.4. After the emergency
B.1. Data Entry	B.2. Data Entry	Thank you			

The first step to properly establish the governance of given data flows is to identify data subjects and holders and to build up a paradigm aiming to protect and empower their fundamental rights.

Data collection can be enabled during the emergency directly from data subjects (for personal data) and data holders (for non-personal data) under the public interests' legal bases or through intermediates that could either belong to first responder or being automatically collected by wearable and allied technologies.

Select a Collection

- Collection during the emergency from data subjects through TRIAGE apps
- Collection from first responders in loco or through allied technologies
- Data generated by the allied technologies set for other purposes

How to ensure data subjects rights	Privacy policy clause: Your personal data will be collected for the purposes of managing this emergency, for further information and details please visit our website or ask the available operator.
How to ensure data subjects rights	Your personal data will be processed by the competent authorities and organizations, through instructed and authorized staff. For further information and details please visit our website or ask the available operator.

Figure 1 – DMP: Collection of data tab

The second part includes a data entry tool aiming to provide the possibility for any user to develop a data management plan and been guided by the options that the SSSA unit provided considering the VALKYRIES experience.

Task / Deliverable / Experiment	Name dataset
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Types and formats of data generated / collected	During the research: where do you store your data
<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px;"><ul style="list-style-type: none">PDFDocAudioVideoPicturesOther (specify)</div>	<input type="text"/>
	<input type="text"/>
	Origin / Sources of the data
	<input type="text"/>
	Specify *
	<input type="text"/>

Figure 2 – DMP: Data entry window

By submitting the wizard, the user will download a PDF file with the newly entered DMP data.

6. Section 2: Protocols for Innovators and other guidelines

The Protocols section is available here: <https://demo.valkyries-h2020.eu/protocols.html>

It includes a series of guidelines and instructions to drive the ethical-legal compliance for R&D&I starting from the VALKYRIES experience on data management for disasters recovery.

The guidelines are addressing three different steps of an R&D&I life-cycle, including the preparatory activities, the solution development, and the application/usage in order to help innovators to be prepared for the possible ethical legal conditions and requirements to be fulfilled during the development activities.

PROTOCOLS FOR INNOVATORS

Introduction | 1. Preparatory activities | 2. Development | 3. Application/Usage | Thank you

Dear user,

This is a demo including checklists and guidelines applicable to any Research & Development & Innovation context to address ethical legal compliance.

Please feel free to follow the check-list, save your answers and add comments and feedback according to your experience.

No personal data are processed unless you'll leave personal information in comments sections. Your IP is tracked only for the purposes to complete the check-list, then it will be immediately cancelled.

These guidelines have been developed in the context of D1.4 and D1.18. If you wish to receive updates on the project, please do not hesitate to contact us <https://www.valkyries-h2020.eu/Contact.html>

CANCEL NEXT

Figure 3 – Protocol for innovators

This section is particularly useful as it sets in a practical way how to deal with the European Data strategy in a concrete and practical scenario of R&D&I development.

In fact, for each relevant legislative initiative a list of suggestions and best practices will open by a simple click on the screen.

Introduction | 1. Preparatory activities | 2. Development | 3. Application/Usage | Thank you

This step refers to the workplan development for a technology solution. According to the risk-based approach, a continuous assessment of the impact on fundamental rights shall be introduced in the life-cycle in order to properly implement technical and organisational safeguards to mitigate the identified and ongoing risks.

The following checklist could be followed in the development of the workplan either for the by *design* dimension or for the by *default* one.

- 1. Mapping the ethical legal framework applicable to the given technology. In particular, verify whether you need to comply with EU Regulations / Directives and national implementations regarding:
 - Personal data under EU Regulation 2016/679, considering the following grounds:
 - i. Purposes and means of data processing to establish how to protect the availability, confidentiality, and integrity of data.
 - ii. Nature of data to combine GDPR conditions with possible national safeguards in case of "sensitive data"
 - iii. Legal basis of data also to establish the governance in case of multi-party sharing agreements
 - iv. Conditions to process cross-border data flows
 - v. Conditions for the possible secondary use of data to check legal basis, governance, safeguards (e.g. pseudonymisation)
 - vi. Contents for the privacy information to data subjects
 - Non-personal data flows under the EU Regulation 2018/1807, considering the following grounds:
 - Sharing personal and non-personal data flows under the Data Governance Act
 - Artificial Intelligence

Figure 4 – Protocol for innovators: development tab

7. Section 3: Ethics and Diversity in Research and Management activities checklist

The Ethics and Diversity tool is available at this link <https://demo.valkyries-h2020.eu>

This section includes the checklist that any R&D&I coordinator could follow in order to address the ethical legal issues related to the inclusiveness and diversity grounds of assessment referred to the life-cycle of the activities or to the work environment within her/his team / consortium.

The guidelines and suggestions are addressed to the three main steps of a project development (preparatory activities, research development, dissemination) in alignment with the research results included in D1.6 and D1.19. In addition, it includes a section entirely dedicated to the team management, addressing not only gender-related issues but the possible vulnerabilities experienced from the ethical legal discussions arisen in the VALKYRIES context.

The screenshot shows a web-based checklist interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with six tabs: 'Introduction', 'i.1. Preparatory activities', 'i.2. Research development' (which is highlighted in green), 'i.3. Dissemination', 'ii. Research Team Management', and 'Thank you'. Below the navigation bar, the main content area contains the following text and form elements:

In the development of technologies, including AI-based solutions, gender-related and diversity issues constitute a relevant ethical legal issue to address also from a technical viewpoint. In order to promote equality and diversity, in fact, it is necessary to assess the risk of generating bias through the data processing activities. To this end, it is necessary to undertake a tailored assessment:

- a. Assess the grounds of discrimination in the data collection and justify them in order to avoid bias in the automated decision-making
- b. Assess the grounds of discrimination in the data processing activities in order to avoid bias in the automated decision-making
- c. Check the data generated by the automated decision-making in order to avoid further bias

Will you follow a specific checklist / guideline / recommendation / standard? *

Yes No

Is your system continuously trained by new data? *

Yes No

Figure 5 – Ethics and Diversity tool

The subsection dedicated to research team management identifies also tailored organisational safeguards that might be required also to apply for funds.

In this regard, the ethics and diversity tool for compliance activities becomes a useful methodology to follow of an effective project management.

Introduction	i.1. Preparatory activities	i.2. Research development	i.3. Dissemination	ii. Research Team Management	Thank you
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An inclusive workplace / consortium / team will be more attentive to develop technical solutions that are promoting non-discrimination and diversity. To this end, in order to promote equality and diversity in the team:

- a. Verify whether your organisation has adopted a

Gender Equality Plan (required to apply for some EU programs)

Code of Ethics including gender-related programs

Specific training activities for staff

Specific positive actions

- b. Assess the level of diversity in your consortium and apply measures to establish an inclusive environment during the life-cycle of the research and development (e.g. work-life balance in the workplan; feminine inclusion and leadership in the governance, etc.), by:

Mapping gender representation in the team / Consortium

Mapping inclusiveness in the key-activities and roles of the project

Mapping possible minorities in the team / Consortium

Mapping possible needs in the given need

Mapping the different religious-cultural holidays

Then

Monitor and report in order to improve inclusiveness within your team and your organisation

Figure 6 – Ethics and Diversity tool: Research Team Management tab

8. Conclusions

This document describes the Data Management Platform and its sections are available on the VALKYRIES website in the section Resources, Demo: <https://www.valkyries-h2020.eu/Demo.html>.

The checklists and guidelines have been developed taking into account the ethical legal challenges faced under the deliverables linked to T1.5 and D3.1 and D3.3.

The usability of the platform has been internally tested as well as during the fourth ethical-legal workshop, where it has been suggested also to further exploit the tools as training and didactic materials for projects and innovation management.

1. Annex A – Glossary

Acronym	Description
DMP	Data Management Plan
GDPR	EU Regulation 2016/679 on General Data Protection Regulation
R&D&I	Research and Development and Innovation

Table 2 - Glossary